

other panicles were left for cross-pollination with V20B.

V20A plants were harvested individually at maturity and the seed set on bagged and open-pollinated panicles was counted to determine the extent of out-

crossing. Seed set for V20A varied from 0.59% at 100 cm to 2.51% at 20 cm from the pollen source (see table).

Low seed set may have been caused by small number of pollen parents (25 plants), improper synchronization of

flowering because there were only 5 days between planting of V20A and of V20B, poor panicle exertion of V20A, and lack of supplementary pollination (e.g. rope pulling, flag leaf clipping). □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

A new cold-tolerant rice for Indonesia

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An improved, cold-tolerant rice line was developed by IRRI and the Indonesian National Rice Improvement Program, and released as a commercial variety by the Indonesian Ministry of Agriculture in 1981 (see table).

The new cultivar, named Batang Agam, was selected from the cross Sirandah Merah/IR2153-159-1-4, made in 1975 at IRRI, and identified as IR7712. F2 seeds were sent to Indonesia and grown at the Sukarami and Ciwalen experimental stations as a bulk population

(entry B29686) during the 1975-76 wet season. Selected progenies were advanced and tested until 1981 when an outstanding line, B29836-Sr-13-4-1-5, was selected and named for release.

Batang Agam is recommended as a cold-tolerant cultivar for the cool tropics

between elevations 900 and 1,200 m or below 900 m where blast (BI) is not severe. It is high yielding, but susceptible to B1 and brown planthopper; moderately resistant to bacterial leaf blight; and resistant to tungro virus. It has medium maturity and good grain quality. □

Agronomic characteristics of Batang Agam, compared with 2 local cultivars at several high elevation sites (900-1,500 m) in West Sumatra.

Agronomic characteristic	Batang Agam	Adil	Semeru
Tillers (no.)	19	20	30
Plant ht (cm)	90-95	76	72
Maturity (d)	153-159	163	165
Blast reaction ^a	S	S	S
Sterility (%)	18.3	27.5	40
1000-grain wt (g)	28	30	31
Amylose (%)	24	22	28
Straw wt (t/ha, wet)	28	35	16
Grain yield (t/ha)	4.69	2.35	3.12

^aS = susceptible.

IR24 selections for cold tolerance

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IR24 is a photoperiod-insensitive high yielding rice with long, slender, translucent grains; good cooking quality; and low amylose content. It also has good disease and insect resistance, but is susceptible to low temperatures. To induce cold tolerance we treated husked and dehusked seeds for 4 h with different concentrations of the chemical mutagens ethyl methane sulfonate (EMS) and diethyl sulfate (dES).

M₂ seeds were germinated at low temperatures (10 ± 1 °C) and screened for low temperature tolerance. Reaction was compared to that of Japanese cold-

tolerant varieties Ishikari and Matsomae and rated using cold tolerance value (CT):

$$CT = \frac{\text{percent emergence}}{\text{days of incubation}}$$

CT was low for almost all M₂ lines; a few had increased CT. When husked seeds

were treated with 0.2 and 0.4% EMS and dehusked seeds were treated with 0.2% EMS and 0.4% dES, CT increased (see table). □

Table continued.

Germination capacity of treated M₂ lines of IR24 at low temperatures.

Treatment	CT ^a
<i>Husked</i>	
Only buffer solution	1.50
EMS	
0.2%	1.58
0.4%	1.67
0.6%	1.17
0.8%	1.33
dES	
0.02%	1.42
0.04%	1.08
0.06%	1.42
0.08%	1.50

Treatment	CT ^a
<i>Dehusked</i>	
Only buffer solution	1.42
EMS	
0.2%	1.58
0.4%	1.33
0.6%	1.00
0.8%	1.17
dES	
0.02%	1.33
0.04%	1.50
0.06%	1.17
0.08%	1.08
<i>Control</i>	
Check (no mutagen)	
Ishikari	3.00
Matsomae	2.08

Continued in next column

^aCold tolerance value.